

MEN4DEM

SAFE RESEARCH ETHICS FRAMEWORK

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MEN4DEM

ABOUT MEN4DEM

MEN4DEM (2025-2027) is an innovative collaborative co-creation project that involves six partner universities as well as a theatre group and a gender justice organization. The consortium studies various manifestations of masculinities in politics. Based on mixture of academic, activist and artistic knowledge MEN4DEM will develop concrete tools to support democratic masculinities in Europe. The project was funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (grant number 101177356). The project website is: www.men4dem.eu.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
MEN4DEM	Masculinities for the Future of European Democracy

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Researcher safety in Europe is under threat. Scholars are increasingly confronted with hate, intimidation, and other forms of violence—especially those who study politically sensitive topics such as far-right extremism. Despite escalating risks, systematic approaches to protect researchers remain scarce. Responsibility for safeguarding academics is contested, and ethical protocols continue to prioritize participant safety while neglecting the vulnerabilities of researchers themselves.

In this report, we:

- Analyze existing approaches to researcher safety and ethical protocols, particularly those focused on conducting difficult research, e.g., terrorism, authoritarianism, extremist movements;
- Demonstrate the value of Feminist Care Ethics as a framework for developing and implementing research(er) safety protocols;
- Apply this framework in practice through the creation of a Researcher Safety Helpdesk, tailored to the MEN4DEM consortium.

We argue for a Feminist Care Ethics approach that centers relationships, interdependence, and context as the basis for ethical decision-making. Feminist Care Ethics explicitly addresses gender, power, and oppression. This is a meaningful approach to manage risk and harm while distributing responsibility across institutions, research teams, and individuals. As such, it counters universalist, impersonal frameworks that overlook inequality and that are often found in institutional approaches to ethics and researcher safety.

Our methods reflect the Feminist Care Ethics approach. Alongside desk research, we used co-creative self-study to foreground the lived experiences of consortium members. Through surveys and collaborative workshops, researchers, artists, and activists collectively mapped fears, risks, and unmet needs. This process generated insight into inequalities within the consortium. For instance, protections available to those researchers who are unaffiliated with academic institutions are uneven. At the same time, the self-study was, in itself, an embodiment of Feminist Care Ethics.

The concrete outcome of this report is the MEN4DEM Researcher Safety Helpdesk, a practical infrastructure designed for an interdisciplinary community of academics, artists, and activists. The Helpdesk equips researchers with resources to **learn and empower** – through academic and practical guides, tailored trainings, and an accessible events calendar—and to **get help when needed**, via country-specific directories of support services at the team, institution, and national level, alongside peer-based mechanisms such as intervision groups and check-in sessions. Together, these tools strengthen prevention, preparedness, and response, while ensuring that care and safety are a shared responsibility across the consortium. Thus, by embedding care into its design, the Helpdesk models researcher safety as a collective, democratic process, rather than an individual burden.

While developed for MEN4DEM, this framework and toolset provide a transferable model for research consortia and institutions facing the challenges of conducting politically sensitive or high-risk research. This report extends an invitation to other research consortia to adapt and build on

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this model. It presents a roadmap grounded in the materials and processes that shaped the MEN4DEM Helpdesk, including scenario-planning activities, surveys on risks and needs, and the role of co-creation embedded into the consortium's first meeting. By sharing both the outcomes and the methods that supported the development of the Helpdesk, the report provides a foundation that others can draw on to design researcher safety infrastructures tailored to their specific contexts.

1. INTRODUCTION

How can and should scholars protect themselves, their research participants, and non-academic collaborators in heightened times of backlash? What do they need to feel safe and care for themselves and others? The question of care throughout the entire research process, from initiation to dissemination and publication of results, is particularly relevant for scholars studying high-risk or controversial topics. In the current political climate, research on gender has become such a field. Researchers working on gender are increasingly targeted by ‘anti-woke’ actors—individuals or groups who actively oppose gender equality, diversity, and social justice, and who often align themselves with authoritarian, nativist, and far-right discourses.

The MEN4DEM project investigates how anti-democratic masculinities influence democratic systems. The project draws on rigorous academic interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research to develop concrete interventions (Besta et al. 2025). The goals of MEN4DEM stand in direct opposition to the ideological agendas of many far-right movements, which aim to shift discursive boundaries, normalize previously unacceptable speech, and establish cultural and political hegemony. MEN4DEM’s efforts to uphold and promote European democratic values such as pluralism, justice, and gender equality may challenge far-right efforts to reshape public discourse and institutions. In this light, the project is likely to face resistance—and potentially active backlash—from actors interested in preserving and expanding their influence.

In fact, early resistance to MEN4DEM has already materialized. In March 2025, just two months into the project, a Christian-Democratic Member of the European Parliament (MEP) publicly targeted MEN4DEM by posting a letter inquiring about ‘the financing of wokeism’ to the European Commission on the platform X. This ignited widespread media coverage and hateful responses across Europe, including in Belgium, France, Georgia, Greece, and Ireland. While we anticipated strong reactions to the dissemination of our results, this premature backlash underscored the urgency of addressing research(er) safety in a climate where such backlash can occur even before data collection has begun.

Given the escalating risks, this report addresses the ethical and moral imperative to mitigate potential harm to the best of our ability against the MEN4DEM consortium’s transdisciplinary community—including researchers, support staff, artists, and activists. Traditional academic systems, with their impersonal, one-size-fits-all frameworks, often fail to recognize the specific, intersectional challenges faced by those conducting high-risk or politically contentious research (Brannelly 2018, 374). Existing ethical protocols typically prioritize the safety of research participants over the vulnerabilities of researchers themselves. These protocols often focus on academically affiliated researchers, leaving citizen researchers, or field research assistants—who are frequently more vulnerable—without adequate support (Naufel and Beike 2013). As a result, systematic and comprehensive approaches to research(er) safety are severely lacking.

In response, we propose and implement a Feminist Care Ethics framework for research(er) safety ethics. The Feminist Care Ethics framework prioritizes relational responsibility, attentiveness to vulnerability, and the recognition of power dynamics within the research process. The framework challenges traditional ethical approaches in academic institutions to safety. We emphasize the need

for researchers, research teams, and institutions to recognize and actively support all those engaged in high-risk research, particularly those in precarious or marginalized positions.

The aim of this report is threefold. First, we need to know what is already in place. To this end, we analyze existing approaches to researcher safety and ethical protocols. Second, we intend to demonstrate the value of a Feminist Care Ethics framework for developing and implementing researcher safety structures and protocols. Third, the goal is to apply the Feminist of Care framework in practice. We achieve this by presenting a structure for a Researcher Safety Helpdesk, which MEN4DEM has installed for its consortium.

Four overarching questions guide the report:

1. What are the risks and challenges that researchers face who conduct politically sensitive or high-risk research?
2. How do existing ethical protocols and institutional policies address researcher safety, and where do they fall short in supporting those engaged in politically sensitive or high-risk research?
3. How can we apply a Feminist Care Ethics framework to create practical, effective safety protocols and support structures that account for the vulnerabilities of researchers from various disciplines and across career stages?
4. How can other research consortia and groups facing similar risks and challenges use practical tools, such as the Researcher Safety Helpdesk, developed for MEN4DEM?

To answer these questions, we analyzed academic literature on safety infrastructures and ethical frameworks for conducting sensitive research, such as terrorism, authoritarian regimes, and extremist movements. We also analyzed good practices from a wide variety of research institutions worldwide, including organizations focused specifically on promoting researcher safety, as well as partners in the MEN4DEM project. Additionally, we conducted an extensive self-study within the consortium, including surveys, co-creation workshops, and interviews. We grounded our process in a Feminist Care Ethics approach that emphasizes relational responsibility, active listening, and attentiveness to the unique vulnerabilities of researchers, activists, and artists involved in the consortium. By centering lived experiences and collaborative reflection, we improved our collective understanding of risk. Through this overall process, we embodied the values of care, solidarity, and mutual respect in the development of researcher safety strategies. A concrete outcome of these exercises is the establishment of a Researcher Safety Helpdesk.

Next, we outline our theoretical point of departure regarding harm, risks, and care, drawing on the literature on the ethics of care and feminist theory. Subsequently, we describe the methods that MEN4DEM is using for risk assessment. The final two sections present the outcome of those self-studies and a blueprint for a researcher safety helpdesk. The resources are developed for MEN4DEM but are also applicable to other scholars and projects studying high-risk topics at European Union academic institutions.

2. HARMS, RISKS, AND CARE

In recent years, threats to academics working at universities in Western democracies have significantly increased (Flaherty 2017; Nogrady 2024; Oksanen et al. 2022). Ranging from intimidating messages to reputational smear campaigns and physical attacks, academics face significant challenges to their safety and, in some cases, the safety of their families (Nogrady 2024). Threats have a considerable impact on scholars across various disciplines (Flaherty 2017), including the social sciences (Oksanen et al. 2022). Scholars working on topics considered 'woke'¹ such as gender, sexuality, and diversity, are more likely to be the target of coordinated attacks (Brown 2023; Vaughan 2023). Scholars researching the far-right draw parallels to the challenges and dangers of conducting research in conflict zones (Pearson et al. 2023; Vaughan 2023; Ashe et al. 2021).

Researchers' safety should be a concern for academics and institutions. Attacks have a profoundly detrimental impact on the safety and well-being of researchers. Attacks also compromise academic freedom and threaten the creativity and societal value of research (KNAW 2025). Moreover, attacks undermine democratic values, weaken public trust in knowledge, and erode society's ability to address complex challenges (Scholars at Risk 2025; West 2022). They can undermine pluralistic education and representation in academic institutions as they seek to target those whose presence in academia is already precarious. This is particularly the case for scholars who are at the early stages of their careers (Bloor et al. 2010; Brown et al. 2024) and those belonging to marginalized populations (Barlow and Awan 2016; Norocel and Segers 2025).

Anti-gender backlash² is coordinated by actors and groups who identify with identitarian, nationalist, and far-right (Dahl and Kennedy-Macfoy 2020; Kuhar and Paternotte 2017; Zervoulakou, Kesberg, and Mügge 2025) as well as Christian organizations (Butler 2025). Risk associated with researching subjects that were once non-confrontational, or "high risk", such as gender equality, has become more challenging and dangerous to researchers. This development increases researchers' exposure to physical, mental, economic, or reputational harm (Brown et al. 2024; Brechenmacher 2025).

Researchers, academic institutions, and other organizations struggle to ensure the safety of researchers. The neoliberalization of academia has undermined efforts to promote a culture of care, while current demands intensify exposure to risk and harm (Brown and Vaughan 2025). Since the early 2000s, universities have adopted corporate and market-driven practices (Giroux 2002; Magnusson 2000). This 'commercialization of knowledge,' as Scott (2006) calls it, has made teaching, research, and publishing more individualized, competitive, and adversarial. In this climate,

¹ The term 'woke' originated in the 1960s in the Black community to describe individuals who were well-informed or alert, especially regarding racial inequality and injustice ("Wokeism, n." 2023). Today, woke, or 'wokeism' has been misappropriated and weaponized as a discursive and symbolic tool to oppose equity-focused policies and those who promote them (Allen 2023; Clark 2024).

² The anti-gender movement is a global, right-wing, social movement which stands in opposition to concepts it refers to as 'gender ideology' or 'gender theory'--or topics that encompass subjects related to feminism, LGBTQ rights, and 'progressivism' (Corredor 2019). In general, the movement targets politicians, women's rights and LGBTQ+ activists, gender policy officers, and academics who promote gender equality, feminism, and LGBTQ+ rights.

voicing fear, anxiety, or seeking support can be perceived as a career liability (c.f. Ahmed, 2021, 2023). The burden is even heavier for marginalized scholars—women, racialized minorities, and LGBTQI+ academics—who face both institutional power imbalances (Ahmed 2012; DeSouza 2011; Keashly and Neuman 2010) and disproportionate exposure to far-right retaliation and harassment (Massanari 2018; Rambukkana 2019; Gelashvili and Gagnon 2024).

The concepts of risk and harm are integral to the ethical frameworks that govern the design and conduct of academic inquiry. Despite their conceptual proximity, risk and harm entail different considerations and require distinct approaches in ethical assessment. Risk refers to the probability of an adverse event, while harm denotes the realized impact (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research 1974; Directorate General for Research and Innovation 2013). Risks are hypothetical and anticipatory, requiring foresight and strategies to minimize their likelihood of occurrence. Harms are actual or imminent outcomes that call for recognition, mitigation, and remediation (Ness 2001). Distinguishing between the two is essential for developing meaningful oversight and safeguarding both researchers and participants.

Assessing risks and harms requires different tools. Risk assessments focus on what might happen and how likely it is to occur, to prevent or minimize the probability of negative outcomes. Alternatively, harm evaluation and management involve evaluating the actual or potential negative impact on those involved in the research process (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research 1974; Ness 2001). Harm assessments focus on what has happened or could cause real-world damage, regardless of its likelihood, to recognize, reduce, and/or remediate damage that has occurred or is likely to occur. When risk and harm are conflated, ethical review and preparation become imprecise, and blind spots can emerge (Dixon and Quirke 2018).

The lack of attention to researcher safety in ethics review processes is a lack of concern. Scholars in critical gender studies, conflict studies, and extremism research show that ethics procedures often prioritize legality and liability over contextual judgment. These procedures can introduce harms and risks, rather than reduce them (Vaughan 2023; Winter and Gundur 2024; Halse and Honey 2007). For example, rigid consent procedures can feel threatening and can interfere with trust while also making participants feel vulnerable (Caeymaex et al. 2023). At the same time, uncritically requiring informed consent from potentially harmful or maligned participants may put researchers at risk (Fuchs 2018). In general, review boards focus primarily on protecting participants from researcher-induced harm but largely overlook the risks that researchers themselves encounter (Mügge 2013). By framing safety predominantly in terms of participants, ethical procedures often fail to foster researcher and institutional reflexivity about the potential harms researchers may face and the resources they require. As Brown and Vaughan (2025) note in their review of ethical approaches to researching the far right, institutions often lack both knowledge and protocols to support researchers in high-risk settings. This void leads to inconsistent ethical requirements and reviews.

Researcher safety thus remains a gray area in institutional ethics. While participant protection is central to review processes, researcher protection is often minimal, fragmented, and treated as the individual researcher's responsibility (Mattheis 2025). Current approaches focus most heavily on researcher safety in research conducted outside of European contexts. The uneven burden of responsibility also often falls hardest on marginalized and early-career scholars, reinforcing

structural inequalities. Junior scholars, particularly PhD students, are disproportionately exposed to physical and emotional harm in fieldwork (Vaughan 2023). Many early-career scholars are left unsupported when supervisors or principal investigators fail to manage risks effectively (Bloor et al. 2010). Yet, supervisors themselves also lack institutional backing, training, and support. Ultimately, some risks are too significant to handle alone, without the institutional safety and support.

An adequate institutional response requires moving beyond the narrow liability frameworks of current ethics procedures. We argue that a Feminist Care Ethics provides a strong foundation for rethinking risks and harms, distributing responsibility more evenly across researchers, teams, and institutions. With this approach, institutions can treat the safety of participants and researchers as an ethical priority.

3. FEMINIST CARE ETHICS

Feminist Care Ethics engages with the dynamics of gender, power, and structural inequality. This approach is rooted in a gender neutral ethics of care developed in the 1980s in response to the impersonal nature of utilitarian and rationalist ethical approaches (Gilligan 1982; Noddings 1984). At its core, an ethics of care emphasizes human interdependencies and views moral obligations as arising from concrete relationships rather than abstract principles, and is relational at its core (Koggel 1998; Nedelsky 2008). Care ethics emphasizes empathy, attentiveness, and contextually informed decision-making (Keller and Kittay 2017). While care ethics emphasizes relationality and responsiveness, *Feminist* Care Ethics situates these values within broader social and political contexts.

Feminist Care Ethics calls attention to the unequal distribution and undervaluation of care in patriarchal systems (Robinson 2015; Tronto 1993). This prism makes the harms visible that are overlooked by bureaucratic and universalist models prevalent in academic institutions (Brannelly 2018; Tronto 2010). The approach prioritizes empathy, active listening, and the cultivation of supportive relationships between students and teachers, researchers and supervisors, and participants. The aim is to foster environments grounded in trust and mutual respect within institutions.

Feminist care-centered leadership catalyzes institutional change that extends beyond the university into broader communities (Schultz 2022). The political roots of Feminist Care Ethics are central to its potential to promote social justice and transformation (Robinson 2015; Brannelly 2018). Feminist Care Ethics is particularly useful for research projects—such as MEN4DEM—that are explicitly feminist in their objectives and oriented toward dismantling harmful practices that undermine democracy and inclusivity. In this research context, the personal risks and emotional labor that researchers face are not incidental but are shaped by the same gendered power dynamics under investigation.

Current institutional approaches to researcher safety—where present—tend to be shaped by neoliberal logics that emphasize individual responsibility, liability management, and marketized notions of research impact. This approach often isolates researchers, framing risk as a matter of personal preparedness or resilience, rather than a collective, structural concern. Feminist Care Ethics offers a crucial alternative to this approach (Brannelly 2018, 374). It reveals the emotional, relational, and structural factors that influence risk and safety. At the same time, it foregrounds the need for collective responsibility, attentiveness to power dynamics, and the cultivation of caring, supportive environments. Feminist Care Ethics emphasizes interdependency and vulnerability as universal aspects of the human condition, highlighting the need for structural solutions to address them (Butler 2018). A Feminist Care Ethics calls on a shared responsibility for *all* members of the academic community to cultivate an inclusive and responsive environment (Tronto 1993; 2013).

Figure 1. Five Tenets of Feminist Care Ethics

Figure 1 shows the five overlapping tenets of Feminist Care Ethics (Tronto 1993; 2005; 2010; 2013).

1. Attentiveness shows that we care *about* something. It is recognition of care and requires noticing and acknowledging the needs of others. (Tronto 2005, 16)
2. Responsibility is an act of care *for* someone or ourselves. This means taking and accepting responsibility, specifically a personal commitment to care, rather than a passive obligation that usually flows from legal protocols (Tronto 2005, 16).
3. Competence relates to caregiving. A caregiver should possess the necessary skills and knowledge to provide adequate care (Tronto 2005, 17).
4. Responsiveness relates to *receiving* care and is a check mark to evaluate how well the care provided meets the care needed. Caregivers need to be attentive to the responses of those they care for and adapt their actions based on input and feedback (Tronto 2005, 17).
5. Solidarity is the recognition that caring *for* is a collective responsibility that requires trust, mutual respect, and democratic solidarity (Tronto 2010, 162; Tronto 2013).

To embed a Feminist Care Ethics in an academic institution, or research project like MEN4DEM, we need to be mindful of three institutional principles (Tronto 2010, 162):

- *Politics*: care is embedded in relations of power and must be debated, and dialogued democratically.
- *Particularity and plurality*: care needs vary depending on the context and individual identity; care is not a one-size-fits-all.
- *Purposiveness*: Institutions and organizations must be explicit and intentional about the *purpose* of care.

Table 1 presents the Feminist Care Ethics framework for MEN4DEM, drawing on Tronto's work. In this framework, care is not confined to interpersonal good intentions but is structurally embedded.

In any academic context, but specifically within MEN4DEM, this means that we recognize the importance of care. And that we are attentive and cognizant of the specific needs of the entire team. Moreover, we make care a shared **responsibility** through core policies, guidelines, and resources. Effective caregiving requires **competence**, which is supported by continuous, adequate, and available training, staffing, and support systems. Reflexivity and adjustment through continued consultations demonstrate a commitment to **responsive care**. Finally, a shared project against harm and the promotion of equity, justice, and democratic participation contribute to **solidarity** across the MEN4DEM consortium.

Table 1. Integrated Feminist Care Ethics Framework

Ethical Element	Institutional Principle	Institutional Approach	MEN4DEM Approach
Caring about (Attentiveness)	Particularity and Plurality	Attention to diverse, context-specific care needs.	Co-creation workshops with MEN4DEM community on topics of risk, harm, and care.
Caring for (Responsibility)	Politics	Collective and equitable responsibility. Identify power imbalances within and outside the institution and/or organization.	Risk, harm, and needs assessments; protocols for internal communications; installation of Researcher Safety Helpdesk.
Care giving (Competence)	Purposiveness	Clarity on the purpose of care and the resources provided at all levels (institutional, research group, and personal).	Care goals and resources, including helpdesk training, are informed by inclusive assessment workshops and surveys.
Care receiving (Responsiveness)	Plurality and Purposiveness	Institutions remain responsive to care experiences through ongoing reflexivity and feedback from recipients and caregivers.	Intervision sessions are open to all members, focusing on caregiving and care resources.
Caring with (Solidarity)	Politics	Solidarity and collective decision-making foster care arrangements that are just, inclusive, and sustainable.	Representatives from each team (Data and Ethics Committee) make joint decisions for care ethics and safety.

Source: Tronto 1993, 2005, 2010, 2013

Building on the principles of the Feminist Care Ethics, which emphasize relationality, interdependence, and the recognition of power dynamics in ethical decision-making, we have

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sought to translate these ideals into concrete action. The feminist care approach stresses that ethical responsibility cannot rest solely on individuals but must be shared across the structures and relationships within academic and research environments. This framework shaped the development of the MEN4DEM Researcher Safety Helpdesk. Drawing on collaborative and attentive methods that fostered solidarity and a sense of shared responsibility for promoting researcher safety in the MEN4DEM project. Ultimately, the Helpdesk embodies the values of Feminist Care Ethics by providing a collaborative and responsive infrastructure that empowers researchers to manage risks and access the necessary support.

4. METHODS

Feminist Care Ethics underpins our search for what MEN4DEM members need from the researcher safety helpdesk. Guided by the ethos that care is a collective responsibility, we developed a methodology that prioritizes the lived experiences of researchers, activists, and artists within the MEN4DEM community. To achieve this, we employed a co-creative self-study approach, which involved a participatory process where researchers, artists, and activists collaboratively identified fears, risks, and unmet needs related to their safety and well-being. Our participatory approach enabled us to surface critical insights such as the disparities in protections for unaffiliated researchers. It served as a concrete enactment of Feminist Care Ethics in practice while informing the development of the Helpdesk.

We employed a layered, iterative design in which different methods built on each other to progressively refine our understanding of risks and needs within the MEN4DEM community. Four primary data sources informed the development of the Helpdesk:

1. Desk research of academic and practitioner literature on researcher safety and organizational best practices.
2. Co-creation activities, particularly a scenario planning workshop.
3. Semi-structured interviews.
4. Risk and needs assessment surveys.

The sequences enabled us to transition from a broad mapping of existing practices to a highly contextualized set of resources for the MEN4DEM community (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Methodology Sequence

Desk research acts as a guide and foundation for our methodology. We conducted a literature review of researcher safety in academic research and organizational practice. This informed our assessment of potential risks and harms, as well as our approach to designing the scenario planning workshop, the risks and needs assessment survey, and identifying opportunities for training and other specific resources to be featured in the helpdesk.

Co-creation is a defining feature of the MEN4DEM project and is an anchor to our commitment to a Feminist Care Ethics. Co-creation activities underpin the MEN4DEM project and have been crucial in establishing a Feminist Care Ethics within the project (Bjarnegård and Mügge 2025). Co-creation

is an iterative, reflective process that promotes shared ownership, mutual learning, and a focus on particularities—all of which are essential for the development and promotion of care throughout the research process (Greenhalgh et al. 2016; Smith et al. 2021; Voorberg, Bekkers, and Tummers 2015).

Recognizing the potential risks and harms to all members involved in the research, we held a scenario planning workshop at the MEN4DEM project kickoff. The workshop was attended by approximately 35 participants who work in academia, activism, theatre or a combination thereof in six European countries. Foresight and scenario planning exercises are rooted in understanding how and why the future might differ from the present, urging individuals to consider the long-range future and develop a strategic posture of reaction by analyzing and preparing for multiple possible futures (US Office of Personnel Management, n.d.).

Following a short introduction to foresight methods, participants were divided into six mixed groups and tasked with envisioning the conduct of research under three different future scenarios: optimistic, realistic, and pessimistic (Appendix I). Each group worked through guiding questions across four dimensions of the research process—data collection, data analysis, dissemination, and credibility—and then presented their findings. The exercise served as an activation activity and a reflective activity. Activation, as it brought potential risks and harm to the attention of those involved in MEN4DEM, which they had likely not thought about deeply up to this point. Reflective, as it enabled members of the research community to consider vulnerabilities and (in)accessible resources/needs.

Insights from the desk research and scenario planning highlighted the need for even more targeted data on the potential risks and resources available to the MEN4DEM community members. We combined the concerns raised in the co-creation with desk research to develop a comprehensive survey. The questionnaire included 150 questions across two main sections (Appendix II): (1) risk and needs across the research process, (2) dynamics and risks within the team. The survey draws on established frameworks, including the International Science Council (2017), University of Essex Research Risks Guidelines (2025), and the University of New Hampshire's Fieldwork Safety Plan (2024).

The first section asks participants to identify risks across six categories—**social, legal, economic, reputational, safeguarding, and health and safety—mapped** onto five stages of the research process: data collection, data analysis, write-up, publication, and communication and dissemination (Appendix III). Survey participants were presented with a matrix of the research process and the harm typology (Table 2).

Table 2. Risk and Harm Assessment Matrix

	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Write-up	Publication	Communication
Social Risks/Harms					
Legal Risks/Harms					
Economic Risks/Harms					
Reputational Risks/Harms					
Safeguarding Risks/Harms					
Health & Safety - Locational Risks/Harms					
Health & Safety - Activity Risks/Harms					
Health & Safety - Physical Risks/Harms					

To structure responses, we embedded the so-called five ‘P’s (Mergaert, Linková, and Strid 2023) into the survey: prevention, processing, protection, provision of service, and partnerships (Table 3). For each identified risk, respondents were asked to name the challenge and consider what preventative measures, processing tools, protective mechanisms, services, and partnerships are currently in place, or would be needed. Combining the typology of risks with the Ps framework enabled us to determine both the types of vulnerabilities researchers face and the practical resources, relationships, and responsibilities needed to address them.

Table 3. Five 'Ps' Framework

Category	Description
Prevention	Measures that raise awareness promote changes in the social and cultural behavior of all members of the institutional community.
Protection	Measures that ensure safety and meet the needs of (potential) targets, victims, and survivors.
Processing	Recognizing, interpreting, and responding to intimidation and harassment to support researchers’ well-being.
Provisions of Service	Services that are provided to targets, victims, survivors, families, and bystanders. Includes the professionals and tools within these services.
Partnerships	The involvement of relevant actors at all levels, including government agencies, civil society organizations, service providers, trade unions, staff, and student associations.

Adapted from (Mergaert, Linková, and Strid 2023, 4)

The second section of the survey focused inward on research teams. This section had research teams reflect on power dynamics, cultural and identity-based concerns, behavioral expectations, communication protocols, and mental health safety within their teams. Each team was required to draft internal communication and escalation plans, as well as to outline mechanisms for promoting and providing mental health awareness and support throughout the project. The two-pronged survey approach emphasized the shared responsibility for ensuring researcher safety across the MEN4DEM research community, starting at the team level and extending to the coordination team. Finally, to facilitate completion, we provided both online and document-based versions of the survey, along with an instructional video. Six academic teams submitted responses.

The insights gathered from the scenario planning exercise, along with the results of the risk assessment survey, helped us identify essential needs and gaps present across the MEN4DEM consortium. These insights were used as the basis for the development of the resources and tools to be included in the Helpdesk, including trainings (prevention, protection, processing), intervention and check-ins (prevention, processing), literature and good practice guides (prevention, protection, processing), as well as a contact directory (provisions of service, partnerships).

5. FINDINGS

5.1 THE BIG FUTURE PICTURE: SCENARIO PLANNING

Scenario planning is a playful tool to dive deep into potential risks and harms. What does the big picture look like in the future? The exercise helped us to understand which team member fears what and why, and what we ultimately needed for the Helpdesk. As we engaged the entire MEN4DEM community—academics, activists, and artists—in open discussions about risks and harms, safety became a collective responsibility. By working through the optimistic, realistic, and pessimistic scenarios, the MEN4DEM community were pushed to move beyond conventional, or often-thought of risks, to identify risks that might occur both in adverse situations or environments, as well as those that might emerge in the best-case environments, or when the project appears to be succeeding. The structured, inclusive dialogue generated a more comprehensive, nuanced picture of the challenges, resources, and conditions required for safe and practical research.

For the majority of the participants, scenario planning was a new exercise. Nevertheless, the experiences with dealing with risks and harms, as well as the resources available, differed. Generally, activists are very experienced. They rely on tools and protocols that they developed themselves individually, within their local organizations, or in transnational collaborations with other organizations. For them, coping with the risks and harms usually follows the ethical principle that safety is a collective responsibility that requires solidarity. For many academics, the need to think through risks and harms is a relatively new reality. Across the board, we observe that qualitative researchers (e.g., ethnographers) tend to have more experience with risk assessments and reflexivity than their quantitative counterparts.

Qualitative researchers typically have more direct contact with participants in potentially dangerous settings and greater experience in assessing qualitative data that may contain sensitive or harmful content. However, experiences with risk and harm are not limited to those doing qualitative or participant-engaged research. Some MEN4DEM scholars who are visible and publicly share their academic views on equality and social justice have experienced intimidation in the past. As a result of the varied backgrounds and experiences, the scenario planning exercise provided an opportunity to both learn and share, as well as to challenge ourselves to think beyond our own lived experiences.

Participant responses to the exercise reveal both enthusiasm and apprehension.³ While many expressed that the workshop was frightening and challenging, nearly all also stated that it was inspiring and engaging. Participants recognized the value of the activity in surfacing both their own blind spots regarding risks and the importance of bringing the research community together to reflect on risks, harms, and preparation collectively.

Several participants highlighted the need for care and preparedness:

³ Participants are cited based on their professional category; no respondent was cited more than once. Activist, Artist, or Academic. Reference: Day 2 Kickoff Survey, Terschelling, Netherlands, January 2025, unpublished survey in author's possession.

The activity taught me that we need to take good care of ourselves and each other. We need to build sustainable caring communities, starting with ourselves. By creating those ripples in the water, picking the low hanging fruit, and extending these to the rest of the world. I have recognized the need to have a serious talk with my team about the risks and how we can prepare for the worst—not to be fearful, but prepared. (Activist)

It demonstrated to me that I need to prepare with my team for the risks. Not to be afraid...but to be sure and ready. (Artist)

Others reflected on the collective knowledge and foresight generated by the group:

The activity helped me recognize that we, together in the group, have more knowledge and ideas of how it looks in the future. (Activist)

We have to be awake to see all the risks that could arise from recent developments in the world. We need to create safety for all. (Academic)

Participants noted that the activity highlighted how not everyone in the MEN4DEM research community has equal access to knowledge about risks and harms, or the resources needed to prevent, address, or protect against them. Several emphasized the importance of being attentive to these inequalities, recognizing both the uneven distribution of awareness and the disparities in available support systems that can help manage potential risks and harms.

I learned there are more risks than we are thinking about. There is an uneven distribution of awareness, experience, and mitigation strategies available to us. This will be important to address. (Academic)

I hadn't fully considered the potential risks outlined in the pessimistic scenario. This showed me that I have to check the resources and support systems available at my university. (Academic)

The exercise taught me that I have to be careful and that not all partners have the same support. (Activist)

Together, these reflections point to three key outcomes of the scenario planning exercise. First, scenario planning fostered mutual understanding and respect for the diverse challenges faced across the research community. Second, it clarified the uneven distribution of resources and

support systems within the community, helping to identify who lacks what and where efforts should be made to enhance researcher safety. Third, it highlighted how different members were concerned with various types of risks and harms. These outcomes are foundational to practicing a Feminist Care Ethics, as they promote attentiveness, responsibility, and solidarity, while underscoring the need to build competence and preparedness both within individual teams and across the MEN4DEM community as a whole.

The scenario planning exercise also prompted participants to identify several specific risks and harms, along with the tools they may need to address or navigate these challenges. A key outcome of the group discussions was the collective call for more targeted training sessions. While participants from all three scenarios—optimistic, realistic, and pessimistic—agreed that training would be beneficial, the specific type of training varied between academics, activists, and artists. For instance, artists emphasized the importance of training in security measures and strategies for personal safety when working directly with the public. Academics emphasized the need for support in communication-related activities, including media engagement and online presence. A unifying theme across all groups was the need for training related to mental health, including the development of protocols to ensure team-wide and project-level access to counselling and mental health support.

Specific references⁴ in the group work materials included suggestions such as:

Hire or consult a security company to train all partners, or use them as escorts where needed. (Pessimists Group 1)

Provide online harassment training so that we can learn to de-escalate and respond. (Realists Group 2)

Provide or find emotional support for the researcher. (Optimists Group 1)

In addition to the need for training activities, participants also emphasized the requirement for further clarification on their rights within the project and the broader European Commission framework. Some expressed potential threats to funding, while others highlighted concerns over deadlines and requests for changes within the project due to security concerns. As one team highlighted:

⁴ Groups are cited based on their scenario category and group number, Scenario Group #. The two groups focused on the Realistic scenario are coded Realists Group 1, and Realists Group 2. Reference: Author notes, Terschelling, Netherlands, January 2025, unpublished field notes in author's possession.

There may be a need to ask to change intervention locations, if, for example, political challenges arise that make it illegal or unsafe for researchers to carry out their intended research tasks. (Pessimists Group 1)

Still others expressed the need for a broader awareness of the project and support for its aims and goals from across European networks.

We should collaborate across European networks and across partner organizations and look to engage global, or at least European, watchdog organizations. (Realists Group 1)

Work with others to share examples with other researchers and groups to share how attacks can appear and what to focus on to help protect one another. (Realists Group 2)

Finally, all groups emphasized the importance of maintaining clear and frequent communication about risks and harms to the MEN4DEM community throughout the entire project. One model for doing so—*check-ins*—was introduced by Emancipator, a MenEngage partner of the MEN4DEM project, during the Kickoff Workshop. The daily check-ins facilitated by Emancipator during the MEN4DEM Kickoff Workshop were well received, and participants suggested that check-ins become a core feature of the MEN4DEM project, including through the Helpdesk.

We should implement regular check-ins for researchers and partner communities, including with other sister project partners, if possible. (Realists Group 1)

Researchers, regardless of research activity, should keep a diary of their experiences on the project. This can be used to reflect and share during check-ins with the project or the individual team. (Pessimists Group 2)

The scenario planning exercise directly operationalized the Feminist Care Ethics Framework. Through inclusive dialogue and shared reflections, the MEN4DEM community practiced **attentiveness**. Together, we identified a diverse set of risks, including those that had previously been underappreciated or had an uneven impact on different members of the MEN4DEM community. The exercise also highlighted a commitment to **responsibility** as safety became a collective obligation, rather than an isolated task. The activity promoted **reflexivity** and **competence** building as the community was able to learn from one another, and often expressed a need to change assumptions, check blind spots, and adjust strategies in light of unequal resources and vulnerabilities. Significantly, the exercise reinforced the MEN4DEM commitment to **solidarity**,

equity, and democratic participation by emphasizing that care is a shared political and ethical practice within MEN4DEM.

5.2 SPECIFIC HARMS AND RISKS: CONTEXTS, METHODOLOGIES, AND INSTITUTIONS

The survey focused on our partner organization teams and countries. The survey served as a bridge between the broader discussion of risks and harms among all consortium members and the specific needs and potential risks faced by local teams. The survey provided detailed insights into the risks and harm associated with certain methodologies, including netnography. It also helped us to understand specific contexts. For instance, conducting right-wing research in Poland poses different risks and challenges than conducting right-wing research in Sweden. Finally, the survey was a tool to map (in)access to resources at the institutional and national levels.

Figure 3 details the risk/harm prevalence identified by research teams in the MEN4DEM project, where green represents no risk and magenta represents severe risk. Researchers demonstrated the most concern over activity-based risks to their health and safety, followed by social risks, and then legal risks. Researcher risks associated with activities were identified in every phase of the research. Researchers’ emphasis on activity-related harms and risks is primarily a result of the action-oriented nature of this risk category and the ease with which researchers can identify risks associated with activities, i.e., conducting interviews or speaking in public.

Figure 3. Heat Map of the Prevalence of Identified Risks/Harms across Research Phases

When viewed by the research phase, the results show that researchers are most concerned with potential exposure to risk and harm in the earliest and latest stages of the research project: data collection, communication, and dissemination. Overwhelmingly, however, researchers are concerned with the communication and dissemination phase, and they have identified all eight risk/harm categories as associated with this phase of the project. They reported the most concern around reputational, health, and safety risks associated with activities in this phase.

The teams identified the fewest concerns in the economic risks category and in the data analysis and write-up phase. However, a lack of risk and harm identification within the data analysis and write-up phase may be due to the limited emphasis that ethics communities and research teams

place on these aspects of the research process. It may be easier to consider external threats, such as direct attacks, which are perceived to be less common at this stage. Yet, in this pattern, the cumulative impact that exposure to harmful and hateful content throughout the write-up and analysis phases can have on mood, sleep, and overall mental health is neglected. Thus, they may not accurately represent the actual potential for threat and harm to researchers throughout these phases.

The research teams expressed concern over potential backlash to the project, specifically in terms of reputational harm, particularly during the publication and communication phases of the project.⁵ Connected to the sharing of the research findings and progress through various channels, both academic and non-academic, researchers demonstrated concern over being labeled or defined as “woke”, “trouble-makers”, etc., which some expressed could challenge their ability to be considered for future collaborations, or impact their standing in the academic community, and in the eyes of future funders.

Researching topics connected to gender (and masculinity in particular) could result in researchers being defined as “trouble-makers”, “woke”, etc., either by mass media, politicians/political actors, colleagues, or the general public. (RT03)

There is a risk that researchers will be labeled as 'woke' or 'progressive,' which is not a negative outcome per se, but may be a problem for future collaborations. (RT05)

The nature and the themes analyzed in our section of the project, such as hate speech, radicalization, and extremist narratives, require careful handling to avoid misinterpretation and controversy during public dissemination. (RT02)

Others expressed concerns about the potential for physical and mental health threats during the project's communication phase.

Backlash can eventually result in physical assault, especially during or after public events; but risks can also consist of becoming the object of stalking or other types of violence. (RT03)

Those who recognized risks at the data collection, analysis, and write-up phases were most likely to cite activity-related challenges, both concerning online and offline experiences. Specifically, researchers involved in collecting qualitative data recognized exposure to challenging

⁵ Responses are cited based on unique identifier given to each research team (RT01, RT02, etc.). Reference: Helpdesk Needs & Resources Assessment Survey, 2025, unpublished survey in author's possession.

environments, as well as exposure to violent or discriminatory content. Those involved with the intervention phase of the research – in which MEN4DEM will facilitate Life Action Role Plays, among others – also expressed concern over exposure to misogynistic and hateful opinions.

These same challenges were identified for the analysis and write-up phase of the research. Research teams expressed concern that interacting with qualitative data may create discomfort, frustration, and anger.

The write up will require reading both empirical materials collected, as well as academic literature that may have content that can create discomfort, frustration, and anger. Also writing reports means having good time management which can present challenges when dealing with exposure to unpleasant materials, leading to even further stress. (RT03)

Generally, research teams were able to identify the challenges associated with the actions that they will undertake throughout the research process. Most expectant was the way that interacting with far-right groups might open them to reputational risks, and health and safety risks associated with mental health. Despite this, research teams struggled to identify the economic and legal risks related to the research. This highlights an important gap in the focus of discussions about risks to researchers from the far right within the literature and academic institutions.

What do participants need to prevent, process, and protect against future harm? And, do participants have access to such resources? Research teams struggled to identify prevention mechanisms and often highlighted that the resources they need are not necessarily resources they have access to. This reflects a general lack of attentiveness in many European academic institutions. In fact, when it came to prevention, many researchers felt that they had little to no knowledge of institutional resources or organizational (national or otherwise) support that they could reach out to for prevention or protection. Institutions clearly did not offer training to make participants knowledgeable and thus more competent. Participants stated that they had no knowledge or left these answers blank. After a follow-up, they said they were unable to answer the question due to a lack of information.

I am not aware of organizations, etc. focused on the prevention of risks associated with attacks in the collection of data in online environments. Rather, this is dependent on the researchers and how they carry out the research. (RT06)

I am unaware of what support we have for researchers at the publication stage to contrast, for example, the ‘woke’ labeling that might impact the willingness of funders to support future research, etc. (RT05)

While there are many resources available, it is challenging to find them in one place. Sometimes, when you find them, they are in another language or are not

applicable to your situation. It is a challenge—especially for foreign researchers, staff, and support. (RT04)

At our institution, we have a collection of links to organizations that could support us. But, I am not aware of more than that. (RT01)

Survey participants were inclined to report having resources or tools to manage the risks and harms they had identified throughout the research process. Many cited institutional resources such as support centers, security and safety divisions, as well as university policies around ethical codes and anti-discrimination policies. However, access to, or knowledge of, such resources—even for processing—varied across the research teams.

While some institutions provide access to services and support across the research stages, others have less developed support. For example, in several cases, survey participants indicated that some mental health resources, like counselors or psychologists, were only accessible to PhD students, but not to postdoctoral researchers or faculty members. Still others highlighted evidence of burdens to demonstrate the enactment of anti-discrimination policies or ethics violations at their institutions. Significantly, then, researchers across the institutions demonstrated a lack of comprehensive care and access to *all* the critical tools they might need to promote researcher safety.

The findings from the first section of the survey align with the scholarship on researcher safety for those working on far-right research. This scholarship has demonstrated that those who have encountered mental health issues as well as physical threats are often let down by their institutions, and sometimes supervisors, who are frequently ill-prepared to help them (Bahn 2012; Bloor et al. 2010). These scholars further highlighted that determining *whom* to seek help from is often a challenge (Mattheis 2025). Moreover, a lack of knowledge or awareness of resources reinforces findings that services aimed at preventing or preparing researchers for the risks and harm associated with high-risk research are often patchy, inaccessible, or nonexistent (Mattheis 2025; Smyth and Martin 2024). Chains of command, escalation plans, and, in general, information about researcher safety remain outside the purview of many academic institutions, thereby increasing the risk of harm to researchers working on high-risk topics.

The survey's outcome demonstrated an overall lack of care across the research community. It highlights the need for interventions on behalf of the entire research community—from individual researchers to academic institutions—to ensure that *all* individuals involved in the research process understand their rights, as well as the support available to them. In other words, it represents the need to undertake and provide a holistic care approach centered on competence and responsiveness.

In the second section of the survey, research teams were asked to reflect on power dynamics, cultural and identity-based concerns, behavioral expectations, communication protocols, and mental health safety within their teams. Teams were asked to draft internal communication and escalation plans, as well as to outline mechanisms to promote and provide mental health awareness and support throughout the project.

Responses to this section of the survey primarily focused on identifying power relations within teams and drafting detailed mental health safety plans. While some teams struggled in these areas, we view this not as a weakness but as an essential indicator of where additional support is needed. The diversity of responses highlights that teams are at different starting points regarding critically reflecting on researcher safety within their teams. Rather than signaling disengagement, the unevenness revealed an opportunity. The Helpdesk can act as a guidance tool for these teams, providing practical resources and examples of good practices. In doing so, it can empower teams to recognize and address internal power dynamics more effectively, thereby strengthening their preparedness in communication and mental health safety.

Overall, the survey findings reinforced the importance of a Feminist Care Ethics approach to the development of the Helpdesk. It demonstrated not only the risks that researchers anticipate but also the uneven access to resources and knowledge across the teams. Teams' abilities to identify specific risks, while struggling with others, demonstrate the necessity of attentiveness to diverse experiences and vulnerabilities, as well as the responsibility to provide guidance and tools where gaps exist. Furthermore, the uneven awareness of institutional support systems highlights the need to, where possible, build competence through training and shared resources. Finally, the finding that teams struggled to develop clear communication and mental health plans underscores the importance of reflexivity and responsiveness, and in general, the need to empower teams with more information and knowledge in these areas.

6. OUTCOME: RESEARCHER SAFETY HELPDESK

The Researcher Safety Helpdesk is a practical embodiment of Feminist Care Ethics. It is tailored to the needs of the MEN4DEM community, which we identified through scenario planning and a survey. The Helpdesk integrates attentiveness, responsibility, competence, responsiveness, and solidarity across the MEN4DEM research community. Within the Helpdesk, support is understood as a structured and shared commitment to care for all project members.

The Helpdesk has a two-part structure: **Learn and Empower**, and **Get Help**. Both sections provide resources aligned with the five Ps—*prevention, protection, processing, provision of service, and partnerships* (Figure 4). While it does not deliver direct services in the form of legal action, one-on-one counseling, or remediation, it does offer equitable access to resources, support, and guidance across the consortium. The content is not static and will be updated as needed, depending on changes in requirements, resources, or risks and harms.

Figure 4. Helpdesk Structure and Purpose Overview

Speaking directly to the need for more targeted prevention, protection, processing tools, and partnerships, the **Learn and Empower** section of the Helpdesk provides members of the MEN4DEM research community with access to links to a *Resource Library* and *Trainings*. The Resource Library provides both academic and practical guides on researcher safety protocols and good practices. It also includes internal MEN4DEM resources, such as the Research Assistant Bill of Rights (Appendix IV), mental health plan templates (Appendix V), and a research diary template (Appendix VI). The Training section of the site addresses the calls of the MEN4DEM community for targeted training in two key areas: mental health safety and social media/online threats. The mental health component is based on the principles of psychological first aid (McCabe et al. 2014; Freed 2024). The training aims to equip researchers with the skills to recognize, respond to, and support mental well-being in

the research community. Training for media will focus on strategies to recognize, mitigate, and report digital harassment and its impacts. MEN4DEM members can also suggest the need for additional training to be organized by MEN4DEM, or external training they have found, using a "Suggest a Training" form located in the *Trainings* section.

The **Get Help** section of the Helpdesk provides the community with resources aimed at protection, processing, and provision of service. Within this section, the community has access to *Directories* associated with each country. Country directory pages include chain of command documentation, as well as links and contact information for institutionally-based as well as national service providers. *Support Structures* in the form of intervision sessions and/or check-in sessions will be conducted regularly throughout the MEN4DEM project. Intervision sessions will provide support to consortium members to reflect on their practice, identify new risks and challenges, and promote ongoing attentiveness and reflexivity throughout the project. Check-in sessions, an intervention developed by the MEN4DEM activist partner, serve as a way for consortium members to meet and discuss fears, challenges, and positive feelings about the research project (Schaaf and Mars 2025). Members can find information about upcoming intervisions/check-ins within the Get Help section. MEN4DEM members can also suggest an intervision/check-in session using the "Intervision/Check-In Request Form" located in the Get Help, *Support Structures* section.

Figure 5. View of MEN4DEM Researcher Safety Helpdesk SharePoint Site

Practically, the Researcher Safety Helpdesk operates within a password-protected SharePoint environment, which is managed by the MEN4DEM Data and Ethics Committee. The SharePoint site

has a website-like appearance (Figure 5) and is accessible only to the MEN4DEM research community. The closed-community website structure of the Helpdesk enables users to navigate the various resources at their disposal more easily, while also providing a safe space for uploading and sharing additional resources with the MEN4DEM community.

While this Helpdesk is specifically developed for MEN4DEM, it can serve as a model for other research groups, consortia, or institutions. A Helpdesk in any research context is a concrete tool to operationalize Feminist Care Ethics across all phases of the research project. It embeds care structurally, promotes competence through training and resources, and maintains responsiveness and participatory practices through intervision and check-ins. Engagement with the Helpdesk fosters solidarity among team members. We hope that the Helpdesk inspires administrators to put a Helpdesk in practice, tailored to the needs of their community. In a time when knowledge, democracy, and academic freedom face mounting threats, the Helpdesk stands as a radical act of care—protecting researchers, fostering solidarity, and reclaiming safety as a condition for free and just knowledge production.

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APPENDIX I. SCENARIO PLANNING EXERCISE

Scenario Planning Exercise

Scenario Name: Researcher and partner safety throughout MEN4DEM

Scenario Type: Safety

Description: This scenario planning exercise examines the most-likely scenario for researcher and partner safety. The exercise uses a scenario planning matrix to explore the impacts of anti-democratic political masculinities and far-right political movements on data collection, data analysis, research dissemination, and researcher/project credibility.

Key Drivers of Change

1. Political Polarization
2. Legal Landscape
3. Far-Right Movements
4. Social Media & Technology
5. Institutional Support & Policy

GROUP 1: OPTIMISTIC

Key Drivers of Change Explained

1. **Political Polarization:** Stable political environments in Germany, Sweden, and the Netherlands will allow for safe research and the freedom to challenge far-right ideologies without significant political pushback.
2. **Legal Landscape:** Countries with strong democratic norms, like Germany and Sweden, will offer legal protection for researchers and CSOs, ensuring that their work can be disseminated safely without fear of legal repercussions.
3. **Far-Right Movements:** Fragmented or less politically powerful far-right movements in Germany, Sweden, and the Netherlands will result in less risk for researchers and CSOs. These groups may be less capable of coordinating attacks or influencing political outcomes.
4. **Social Media & Technology:** Digital tools will help researchers and CSOs bypass physical risks and reach a global audience with their findings, while anonymity tools can help protect researchers from digital attacks.
5. **Institutional Support & Policy:** Strong institutional support in democratic nations will empower researchers and CSOs to navigate hostile environments and achieve greater impact. Research will be more likely to shape public policy and contribute to democratic resilience.

Summary of Key Impacts

Research Phase	Description of Key Impacts
Data collection	Access to data remains safe and legally protected, with fewer physical risks in Germany, Sweden, and the Netherlands. Digital tools facilitate data collection without physical exposure.
Data analysis	Mental health support and institutional backing help researchers focus on unbiased analysis. No significant legal barriers to conducting research.
Communication/Dissemination	Researchers can disseminate their work through mainstream academic and media channels with full legal protection.
Researcher & Project credibility	Institutional backing and partnerships with CSOs ensure strong credibility and international recognition.

GROUP 2: REALISTIC

Key Drivers of Change Explained

1. **Political Polarization:** Increasing polarization in countries like Poland, Italy, and Greece will amplify the risks for both researchers and CSOs. These polarized environments can create opportunities for far-right groups to exert political or social influence, which may result in harassment or suppression of research critical of far-right ideologies.
2. **Legal Landscape:** Legal restrictions (e.g., anti-extremism laws, counter-terrorism measures) could severely limit research methods and data collection in countries with authoritarian tendencies, such as Poland and Italy. Researchers may face legal challenges that could delay or suppress the dissemination of their findings.
3. **Far-Right Movements:** The strength and political influence of far-right movements in countries like Poland, Italy, and Greece will present challenges for researchers and CSOs. These movements may escalate violence, harassment, or intimidation against those researching anti-democratic ideologies.
4. **Social Media & Technology:** Social media platforms will offer both opportunities and risks for remote data collection and dissemination. While these platforms allow researchers to engage with a wider audience, they also expose them to online threats and harassment from far-right groups.
5. **Institutional Support & Policy:** Institutional support will be uneven across Europe, with Germany, Sweden, and the Netherlands providing strong backing for democratic research, while Poland and Italy may offer less institutional support or even political interference. Researchers may need to rely more on civil society partners to ensure safety and credibility.

Summary of Key Impacts

Research Phase	Description of Key Impacts
Data collection	Increased risks for direct engagement with far-right groups, particularly in Poland and Italy. Remote data collection via social media and technology is more common, but the risks of digital harassment remain.
Data analysis	Mental health challenges due to online harassment and the emotional toll of working in polarized environments. Self-censorship may arise from legal pressures.
Communication/Dissemination	The potential for censorship and suppression of findings in some countries. Use of social media will be a double-edged sword due to backlash.
Researcher & Project credibility	Far-right disinformation and political pressures could damage credibility in countries with strong far-right movements. Collaborations with CSOs will help maintain credibility.

GROUP 3: PESSIMISTIC

Key Drivers of Change Explained

1. **Political Polarization:** Political polarization may escalate in countries like Poland and Italy, leading to increased repression of academic freedom and attacks on researchers and civil society actors.
2. **Legal Landscape:** Authoritarian legal frameworks in countries with rising far-right influence (e.g., Poland and Italy) may suppress academic freedom and criminalize certain forms of research, especially when it challenges far-right ideologies.
3. **Far-Right Movements:** The growing strength of far-right movements could result in escalating violence or political interference, particularly in countries where far-right actors are embedded in government.
4. **Social Media & Technology:** Far-right groups will leverage social media to target and harass researchers and CSOs. These movements may weaponize technology to disrupt research activities, suppress findings, or undermine researchers' credibility.
5. **Institutional Support & Policy:** In countries with politically hostile environments, researchers and CSOs may lose funding or institutional backing, potentially leading to reputation damage and reduced credibility.

Summary of Key Impacts

Research Phase	Description of Key Impacts
Data collection	Escalating physical threats and digital surveillance could severely hinder direct data collection. Legal restrictions may prevent safe engagement in high-risk environments.
Data analysis	Mental health stress due to online harassment and self-censorship could reduce the quality of analysis. Fear of repression could limit data accuracy.
Communication/Dissemination	Censorship or digital suppression of research findings could limit dissemination. Far-right groups may actively suppress or discredit findings.
Researcher & Project credibility	Far-right attacks and political suppression may result in reputation damage and loss of institutional support, undermining researcher and project credibility.

Overview of Key Impacts: Optimistic, Realistic, Pessimistic

Research Phase	Optimistic	Realistic	Pessimistic
Data collection	<p>In countries with a less polarized political climate (e.g., Germany, Sweden, the Netherlands), researchers and CSOs will have greater access to data and safer engagement with far-right groups due to stronger institutional support and legal frameworks.</p> <p>Digital tools and collaborations with local NGOs will allow safe data collection with minimal physical risk. Social media can be used effectively to gather public data and analyze sentiment without direct contact with far-right groups, minimizing risks.</p> <p>Increased collaboration between researchers and CSOs will foster safe data collection with shared protection strategies.</p>	<p>Political polarization in countries like Poland, Italy, and Greece increases the risks for researchers and CSOs engaging with far-right groups. Legal restrictions (e.g., anti-extremism laws) may limit direct engagement with far-right actors, especially in countries like Poland, making access to data challenging. Social media and technology offer opportunities for remote data collection, reducing physical risks but increasing the potential for digital threats and online harassment.</p> <p>CSOs working with researchers will play a critical role in facilitating safe data collection by acting as intermediaries, but they may also face backlash from far-right groups.</p>	<p>High risks of physical threats and harassment in Poland, Italy, and Greece, where far-right groups are politically and socially entrenched. Legal restrictions in these countries may prevent direct engagement or lead to surveillance of researchers and CSOs.</p> <p>In specific authoritarian contexts, researchers and CSOs may be unable to collect data due to repression or state-sponsored opposition.</p>
Data analysis	<p>Academic freedom and strong institutional support in Germany and Sweden will ensure safe data analysis, free from the threat of political interference or harassment.</p>	<p>Mental health strain may be significant due to the emotional toll of working in a polarized political environment and the constant threat of online harassment.</p>	<p>Increased mental health toll due to relentless online harassment from far-right groups, especially where political and legal tensions are high.</p>

	<p>Mental health resources and peer networks can help researchers cope with stress associated with challenging topics.</p> <p>Data analysis will remain objective and free from the pressures of political interference, especially in countries with democratic institutions that support research autonomy.</p>	<p>Legal pressures in countries with rising far-right influence may lead to self-censorship during data analysis. CSOs could provide crucial mental health support for researchers and fieldworkers, helping them navigate challenges related to psychological stress. However, it may also need access to collaborative resources.</p> <p>The analysis process could be slowed by legal uncertainty or fear of backlash, especially in countries like Poland.</p>	<p>Self-censorship due to fear of legal consequences or reputation damage.</p> <p>Burnout from dealing with a hostile political environment and pressure to alter research conclusions. Data analysis may be compromised by fear of reprisal.</p> <p>Researchers and partners may experience emotional exhaustion from working in highly polarized or oppressive political climates, where institutional support is scarce.</p>
<p>Communication/ Dissemination</p>	<p>Wider dissemination of research in Germany, Sweden, and the Netherlands, where there is strong institutional and political support for academic freedom.</p> <p>Research findings will be used in policy advocacy and counter-extremism strategies, enhancing the impact of the research.</p> <p>International academic networks will provide a platform for disseminating research, ensuring a global reach.</p>	<p>The legal landscape will be a significant driver, with countries like Poland and Italy potentially restricting the dissemination of research critical of far-right movements due to political pressure.</p> <p>Social media may be used to disseminate research findings but could expose researchers to backlash from far-right actors.</p> <p>Institutional support in countries like Germany and Sweden will enable researchers to disseminate their findings through peer-reviewed journals and academic conferences without facing significant challenges.</p>	<p>Censorship of research findings in Poland and Italy, where far-right movements have significant political influence.</p> <p>Political interference and harassment may prevent researchers from publishing or disseminating findings in traditional media outlets or academic journals.</p> <p>Civil society organizations may face backlash for helping disseminate research, with potential legal consequences or political suppression.</p>

			Underground dissemination may become necessary, but it will limit the impact and visibility of the research.
Researcher & Project credibility	<p>High credibility in Germany, the Netherlands, and Sweden, where research on democratic resilience and counter-extremism is valued. Research findings will support policymaking on democracy and extremism, and will be considered highly credible in the international academic community.</p> <p>Institutional backing and public trust in research will remain intact.</p> <p>CSOs will also enhance the credibility of research by supporting it with grassroots insight and on-the-ground knowledge.</p>	<p>Institutional support may be inconsistent in countries with a rising far-right influence, where researchers may face pressure to alter their conclusions or avoid making controversial findings.</p> <p>Social media and technology present both risks (such as online harassment) and opportunities (to establish global credibility through alternative platforms).</p> <p>Research will gain credibility in countries like Germany and Sweden, where academic freedom is protected and where research supports democratic values.</p> <p>Collaboration between academia and civil society may enhance credibility and offer protection for the research.</p>	<p>Severe reputational damage due to smear campaigns or political backlash from far-right groups, particularly in countries like Poland and Italy, where far-right actors are entrenched.</p> <p>Legal threats or defamation campaigns could undermine the credibility of the research, damaging both the researcher's and the CSO's public image.</p> <p>Researchers or partners may lose funding or institutional support due to political sensitivities surrounding the topic.</p> <p>The research project may be perceived as biased, and public trust in the findings may be diminished.</p>

APPENDIX II. HELPDESK NEEDS & RESOURCES ASSESSMENT SURVEY

Helpdesk Needs & Resources Assessment Survey

Welcome to the MEN4DEM Researcher Safety Helpdesk needs and resources assessment survey.

This survey was designed to gather information from academic partners in the consortium regarding the various risks and resources available to members of the research teams across our consortium, in order to assist us in the development of the Researcher Safety Helpdesk (WP7).

The survey has several sections, including:

- Team details
- Identifying risk categories and their presence throughout the research process
- Identifying specific risks associated with the risk categories throughout the research process
- Identifying specific risk exposure for team members with marginalized identities
- Outlining risks and procedures for internal team dynamics
- Determining the chain of command and contact persons within your team

There are a total of 176 questions. Do not be alarmed! You will not be asked to answer every question. Rather, depending on the risks you identify, you will be asked to elaborate on those specific selections. You will have 5 weeks to complete the survey.

Please also find [HERE](#) a recording where Brit walks through some logistics and important information.

Should you have any questions or concerns, please direct them to men4dem@uva.nl and use the subject, "Helpdesk Survey".

Thank you in advance for your contributions!

Team Details

Q2.1 Institution/University:

Q2.2 Executive Board member:

Q2.3 Team members: Please list all team members and their position. Members should be listed on separate lines. Example: Brit Anlar, postdoctoral researcher

Q2.4 Work packages involved in: Please list all work packages that your team will participate in, in any capacity (e.g. as WP leader, task leader, data collection, etc.)

Q2.5 What are your team’s responsibilities in this(ese) work package(s)? Select all that apply.

	Work Package Leader	Task Leader	Data Collection	Other
WP1				
WP2				
WP3				
WP4				
WP5				
WP6				
WP7				
WP8				

Q2.6 If you selected other for any work package, please state your role in this/these work package(s).

Q2.7 Please provide the name of your ethics & data management committee member.

Q2.8 Please provide the name of your communications committee member.

Q2.9 Please provide the name of your publications committee member.

Risk Categories and Research Processes

Typical risks that need to be considered as part of research ethics are:

- Social risks: risks that can affect researchers' standing in the community, in their family, and in their job.
- Legal risks: activities that can result in the researcher and / or university committing an offense; activities that could result in a civil claim for compensation.

- Economic risks/harm: financial harm to the researcher and/or university through disclosure or other event.
- Reputational risks: damage to the public perception of the researcher and/or university in the eyes of funders, the research community, and/or the public.
- Safeguarding risks: Risk to researchers of being in a compromising situation, where there might be accusations, or exposure to improper behavior, abuse, or exploitation.
- Health and safety risks: risks of harm to health, physical injury, or psychological harm to the researcher.
- Location hazards - risks associated with where the research is being carried out (e.g. conflict zone; late-night work; social movement/protest).
- Activity hazards - risk associated with the tasks carried out (mentally harmful activities; distressing and stressful work/content; slipping, lifting, carrying, etc.).
 - Distressing and stressful work content can include, but is not limited to, things such as online content that attacks gender identity, race/ethnicity, religious beliefs, etc.
 - Mentally harmful activities can include, but are not limited to, experiencing hate speech, harmful work environments and power dynamics, etc.
- Physical agents of risk - risks associated with the body (excessive noise exposure leading to hearing issues; sexual misconduct; physical assault).

Q3.2 Consider the research activities your team will be undertaking. Please check the box for each of the risk categories (rows) you think might be present at each phase of the research process (columns).

	Data collection	Data analysis	Write-up	Publication	Communication
Social risks					
Legal risks					
Economic risks/harm					
Reputational risks					
Safeguarding risks					
Health and Safety - locational risks					
Health and Safety - activity risks					
Health and Safety - physical risks					

Data Collection Phase

Social Risks (Coll.)

Q4.1 Please elaborate specific social risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.2 Please consider the specific social risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Q4.3 Consider each social risk you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, legal frameworks, or civil society organizations that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Legal Risks (Coll.)

Q4.4 Please elaborate specific legal risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.5 Please consider the specific legal risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Q4.6 Consider each legal risk you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Economic Risks (Coll.)

Q4.7 Please elaborate specific economic risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.8 Please consider the specific economic risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Q4.9 Consider each economic risk you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Reputational Risks (Coll.)

Q4.10 Please elaborate specific reputational risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.11 Please consider the specific reputational risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Q4.12 Consider each reputational risk you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or

resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Safeguarding Risks (Coll.)

Q4.13 Please elaborate specific safeguarding risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.14 Please consider the specific safeguarding risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q4.15 Consider each safeguarding risks you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Location (Coll.)

Q4.16 Please elaborate specific health and safety-location risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.17 Please consider the specific health and safety-location risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q4.18 Consider each health and safety-location risks you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Activity (Coll.)

Q4.19 Please elaborate specific health and safety-activity risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.20 Please consider the specific health and safety-activity risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q4.21 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Physical (Coll.)

Q4.22 Please elaborate specific health and safety-physical risks you foresee for your team throughout the data collection phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q4.23 Please consider the specific health and safety-physical risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or

resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q4.24 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the data collection phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Support/Resources (Coll.)

Prevention (Coll.)

Q4.25 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in preventing the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with category	Risk category	Support location
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Protection (Coll.)

Q4.26 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in protecting against future or further harm from the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Processing (Coll.)

Q4.27 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in processing, or dealing with, the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Limitations (Coll.)

Q4.28

Assess the resources and support you have just outlined. What resources or supports do you think are lacking, or are inaccessible to your team? Please be as specific as possible.

Data Analysis Phase

Social Risks (Analysis)

Q5.1 Please elaborate specific social risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.2 Please consider the specific social risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.3 Consider each social risk you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, legal frameworks, or civil society organizations that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Legal Risks (Analysis)

Q5.4 Please elaborate specific legal risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.5 Please consider the specific legal risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.6 Consider each legal risk you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Economic Risks (Analysis)

Q5.7 Please elaborate specific economic risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.8 Please consider the specific economic risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.9 Consider each economic risk you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Reputational Risks (Analysis)

Q5.10 Please elaborate specific reputational risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.11 Please consider the specific reputational risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.12 Consider each reputational risk you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Safeguarding Risks (Analysis)

Q5.13 Please elaborate specific safeguarding risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.14 Please consider the specific safeguarding risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.15 Consider each safeguarding risks you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Location (Analysis)

Q5.16 Please elaborate specific health and safety-location risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.17 Please consider the specific health and safety-location risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.18 Consider each health and safety-location risks you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

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Health and Safety – Activity (Analysis)

Q5.19 Please elaborate specific health and safety-activity risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.20 Please consider the specific health and safety-activity risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.21 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Physical (Analysis)

Q5.22 Please elaborate specific health and safety-physical risks you foresee for your team throughout the data analysis phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q5.23 Please consider the specific health and safety-physical risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q5.24 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the data analysis phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a

support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Support/Resources (Analysis)

Prevention (Analysis)

Q5.25 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in preventing the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Protection (Analysis)

Q5.26 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in protecting against future or further harm from the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Processing (Analysis)

Q5.27 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in processing, or dealing with, the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Limitations (Analysis)

Q5.28 Assess the resources and support you have just outlined. What resources or supports do you think are lacking, or are inaccessible to your team? Please be as specific as possible.

Write-up Phase

Social Risks (Write up)

Q6.1 Please elaborate specific social risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.2 Please consider the specific social risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.3 Consider each social risk you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, legal frameworks, or civil society organizations that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Legal Risks (Write up)

Q6.4 Please elaborate specific legal risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.5 Please consider the specific legal risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.6 Consider each legal risk you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Economic Risks (Write up)

Q6.7 Please elaborate specific economic risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.8 Please consider the specific economic risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.9 Consider each economic risk you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

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Reputational Risks (Write up)

Q6.10 Please elaborate specific reputational risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.11 Please consider the specific reputational risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.12 Consider each reputational risk you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Safeguarding Risks (Write up)

Q6.13 Please elaborate specific safeguarding risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.14 Please consider the specific safeguarding risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.15 Consider each safeguarding risks you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Location (Write up)

Q6.16 Please elaborate specific health and safety-location risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.17 Please consider the specific health and safety-location risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.18 Consider each health and safety-location risks you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Activity (Write up)

Q6.19 Please elaborate specific health and safety-activity risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.20 Please consider the specific health and safety-activity risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.21 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Physical (Write up)

Q6.22 Please elaborate specific health and safety-physical risks you foresee for your team throughout the write up phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q6.23 Please consider the specific health and safety-physical risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q6.24 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the write up phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Support/Resources (Write up)*

Prevention (Write up)

Q6.25 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in preventing the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Protection (Write up)

Q6.26 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in protecting against future or further harm from the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Processing (Write up)

Q6.27 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in processing, or dealing with, the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Limitations (Write up)

Q6.28 Assess the resources and support you have just outlined. What resources or supports do you think are lacking, or are inaccessible to your team? Please be as specific as possible.

Publication Phase

Social Risks (Pub.)

Q7.1 Please elaborate specific social risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.2 Please consider the specific social risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Q7.3 Consider each social risk you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, legal frameworks, or civil society organizations that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Legal Risks (Pub.)

Q7.4 Please elaborate specific legal risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.5 Please consider the specific legal risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q7.6 Consider each legal risk you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Economic Risks (Pub.)

Q7.7 Please elaborate specific economic risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.8 Please consider the specific economic risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q7.9 Consider each economic risk you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Reputational Risks (Pub.)

Q7.10 Please elaborate specific reputational risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.11 Please consider the specific reputational risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Q7.12 Consider each reputational risk you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or

resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process
...			

Safeguarding Risks (Pub.)

Q7.13 Please elaborate specific safeguarding risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.14 Please consider the specific safeguarding risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q7.15 Consider each safeguarding risks you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Location (Pub.)

Q7.16 Please elaborate specific health and safety-location risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.17 Please consider the specific health and safety-location risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q7.18 Consider each health and safety-location risks you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Activity (Pub.)

Q7.19 Please elaborate specific health and safety-activity risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.20 Please consider the specific health and safety-activity risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q7.21 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Physical (Pub.)

Q7.22 Please elaborate specific health and safety-physical risks you foresee for your team throughout the publication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q7.23 Please consider the specific health and safety-physical risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q7.24 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the publication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Support/Resources (Pub.)*

Preventing (Pub.)

Q7.25 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in preventing the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location
...					

Protecting (Pub.)

Q7.26 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in protecting against future or further harm from the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Processing (Pub.)

Q7.27 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in processing, or dealing with, the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Limitations (Pub.)

Q7.28 Assess the resources and support you have just outlined. What resources or supports do you think are lacking, or are inaccessible to your team? Please be as specific as possible.

Communication Phase

Social Risks (Comm.)

Q8.1 Please elaborate specific social risks you foresee for your team throughout the communications phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.2 Please consider the specific social risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.3 Consider each social risk you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, legal frameworks, or civil society organizations that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Legal Risks (Comm.)

Q8.4 Please elaborate specific legal risks you foresee for your team throughout the communication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.5 Please consider the specific legal risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.6 Consider each legal risk you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Economic Risks (Comm.)

Q8.7 Please elaborate specific economic risks you foresee for your team throughout the communication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.8 Please consider the specific economic risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.9 Consider each economic risk you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Reputational Risks (Comm.)

Q8.10 Please elaborate specific reputational risks you foresee for your team throughout the communication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.11 Please consider the specific reputational risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.12 Consider each reputational risk you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Safeguarding Risks (Comm.)

Q8.13 Please elaborate specific safeguarding risks you foresee for your team throughout the communication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.14 Please consider the specific safeguarding risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.15 Consider each safeguarding risks you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Location (Comm.)

Q8.16 Please elaborate specific health and safety-location risks you foresee for your team throughout the communication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.17 Please consider the specific health and safety-location risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.18 Consider each health and safety-location risks you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Activity (Comm.)

Q8.19 Please elaborate specific health and safety-activity risks you foresee for your team throughout the communication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.20 Please consider the specific health and safety-activity risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.21 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Health and Safety – Physical (Comm.)

Q8.22 Please elaborate specific health and safety-physical risks you foresee for your team throughout the communication phase. Be as specific as possible, highlighting various work package/task activities and why or how these expose the team to these risks as well as exactly what these risks might be.

Q8.23 Please consider the specific health and safety-physical risks you have identified for your team in the previous answer. Give the risk an abbreviated name (column 1), then detail what tools or resources you would need to help (a) prevent, (b) protect against future harm/risk, (c) process/deal with the risk. Note that you can list up to ten specific risks and answers can be essay-length.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Q8.24 Consider each health and safety-activity risks you have identified in the communication phase. Are there legal organizations, civil society organizations, or legal frameworks that might act as a support or resource for preventing, protecting against, and processing this risk? Select all that apply per risk. Please ignore the rows where you do not have a specific identified risk.

Risk Name/Title	Prevent	Protect	Process

Support/Resources (Comm.)*

Prevention (Comm.)

Q8.25 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in preventing the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Protection (Comm.)

Q8.26 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in protecting against future or further harm from the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Processing (Comm.)

Q8.27 Consider the risks you have identified associated with the data collection phase. What organizations, committees, institutions, or legal/binding frameworks are available in your country, university, or department that can help support you in processing, or dealing with, the risks you have identified. Please select the associated risk category (e.g. social, legal, economic...) and the support location (e.g. national, university, departmental) and provide the name or detail of the support/resource and provide a weblink where available.

Risk Name/Title	Title of resource/support	Support weblink	Description of risks associated with	Risk category	Support location

Limitations (Comm.)

Q8.28 Assess the resources and support you have just outlined. What resources or supports do you think are lacking, or are inaccessible to your team? Please be as specific as possible.

Cultural and Marginalized Group Identity Concerns

Q9.1 Is the research being conducted in a context with expectations of strict adherence to "traditional" gender norms? Yes/No

Q9.2 (if previous answer yes) Please describe measures you will take to ensure the safety of team members who may be impacted.

Q9.3 Do you anticipate any safety concerns for members of the research team who may be transgender or nonbinary? Yes/No/Maybe

Q9.4 (if previous answer yes or maybe) Please describe measures you will take to ensure the safety of team members who may be impacted.

Q9.5 Do you anticipate any safety concerns for members of the research team who may be LGBTQIA+? Yes/No/Maybe

Q9.6 (if previous answer yes or maybe) Please describe measures you will take to ensure the safety of team members who may be impacted.

Q9.7 Do you anticipate any safety concerns for members of the research team who hold marginalized racial identity(ies)? Yes/No/Maybe

Q9.8 (if previous answer yes or maybe) Please describe measures you will take to ensure the safety of team members who may be impacted.

Q9.9 Do you anticipate any safety concerns for members of the research team due to religious affiliation/practice? Yes/No/Maybe

Q9.10 (if previous answer yes or maybe) Please describe measures you will take to ensure the safety of team members who may be impacted.

Q9.11 Do you anticipate any safety concerns for members of the research team due to (dis)ability? Yes/No/Maybe

Q9.12 (if previous answer yes or maybe) Please describe measures you will take to ensure the safety of team members who may be impacted.

Q9.13 Mental health is a serious point of concern during this research project, particularly for early career scholars. Please describe measures you will take to ensure the mental health safety of all team members. This could include setting up a mental health safety plan within your team as well as for individual team members (example).

Internal Team Dynamics and Risks

Q10.1 What are the general expectations of behavior while the team is participating in MEN4DEM related research and group activities? How will these be communicated to the team?

Q10.2 What are the expectations around consumption of alcohol? How will these be communicated to the team?

Q10.3 What are your institution's policies around sexual assault and harassment? How will these be communicated to the team?

Q10.4 What are your team's policies around sexual assault and harassment? How will these be communicated to the team?

Q10.5 Please describe any power dynamics that are present within the team, and which may impact team members' sense of safety/empowerment/support.

Q10.6 What are the specific behavioral expectations of those in positions of power within the team? (Ex: PI & other leaders.)

Chain of Command & Contact

If a team member sees/hear/experiences something that concerns them during the MEN4DEM project...

Q11.2 What is the institutional chain of command for sharing this concern?

Q11.3 How should they address this concern with the team lead? Provide name and contact information.

Q11.4 Who is an alternative contact person for concerns? Provide their name and contact information.

Q11.5 If an emergency occurs, who should the members contact with regards the following things. Please provide a name and the best contact information.

Physical injury:

Mental health crisis, or concern:

Incidents of sexual misconduct:

Incidents of discrimination / discriminatory harassment, bias / hate crime:

Legal crisis:

Economic injury:

Q11.7 Please provide a set of university-based emergency contacts for members of your research team (ranging from professors to student assistants). You may provide up to 15 contacts.

Contact/Organization/Institution	Email, Phone, or Weblink	Services Available To: Please select from: all team members; student assistants; phds; postdocs; faculty). List all that apply.

End of Survey.

APPENDIX III. RISK TYPOLOGY AND RESEARCH PHASE DESCRIPTIONS

Appendix Table 1. Risk Typology

Risk Category	Description
Social Risk	Risks that can affect the researcher’s standing in their community, family, or workplace.
Legal Risk	Activities that can result in the researcher and/or university committing an offense; activities that could result in a civil claim for compensation; activities that could lead a participant to disclose criminal activity; activities that expose the researcher to participation in criminal activities.
Economic Risk	Financial harm to participant, researcher, and/or university.
Reputational Risk	Damage to the public perception of the researcher and/or the university through disclosure or other events.
Safeguarding Risk	Risk to researchers of being in a compromising situation, or risk from exposure to improper behavior, abuse, or exploitation.
Health and Safety Risk	<p>Risk of harm to health, physical injury, or psychological harm to the researcher (or participants).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locational hazards – risks associated with where the research is being carried out (e.g. conflict zone; late-night work; social movement/protest). • Activity hazards – risks associated with the tasks carried out (mentally harmful activities; distressing and stressful work/content; slipping, lifting, carrying, etc.) • Physical agents of risk – risks associated with the body (excessive noise exposure leading to hearing issues; physical assault – not limited to sexual assault).

Appendix Table 2. Research Phase Descriptions

Research Stage	Description
Data collection	The systematic process of gathering and measuring information on variables, or subjects of interest. Includes both qualitative and quantitative methods.
Data analysis	The systematic processing and interpretation of collected data to draw meaningful conclusions and answer research questions.
Write-up	The process of organizing the findings into a structured research report, article, or book.
Publication	The formal presentation and submission of research to academic journals or publishers.
Communication / Dissemination	Sharing of research findings beyond academic publication. Can include media talks, social media proliferation of research, academic/non-academic conferences, panels, and/or talks.

APPENDIX IV. RESEARCH ASSISTANT BILL OF RIGHTS EXAMPLE

Preamble

Recognizing the essential role of research assistants in the pursuit of knowledge, and affirming their dignity, safety, and professional development, this Bill of Rights sets forth the fundamental rights to which research assistants are entitled in the conduct of research activities.

For this Bill of Rights, *research assistants* include all individuals contributing to the conduct of research within the MEN4DEM project. This term encompasses traditional academic research assistants, as well as activist and artist partners who participate in data collection and analysis.

Article I. Right to Safety

Research assistants have the right to protection from harm. All risks arising from participants, environments, and research apparatus shall be minimized to ensure their physical and psychological well-being.

Article II. Right to Informed Consent

Research assistants have the right to informed consent regarding their involvement in research activities. Such consent shall clearly document potential risks and benefits, except in cases where withholding certain information is essential to preserve the validity of the study.

Article III. Right to Refusal of Objectionable Activities

Research assistants have the right to decline participation in research tasks or data collection activities they find objectionable. In such cases, an alternative assignment will be provided without penalty.

Article IV. Right to Withdraw

Research assistants have the right to withdraw from a session or study in which they are engaged, at any time and without penalty.

Article V. Right to Counselling and Incident Notification

In the event of harm, research assistants have the right to have the incident formally reported to the appropriate body (e.g., the MEN4DEM Researcher Safety Helpdesk). They also have the right to access intervention and check-in sessions, as well as counselling resources available in their country of operation.

Article VI. Right to Proper Training

Research assistants have the right to adequate training prior to assuming any research responsibilities, ensuring they are prepared for the tasks assigned.

Article VII. Right to Feedback

Research assistants have the right to receive constructive feedback on their performance. Evaluations shall be based solely on established project requirements and demonstrated performance.

Article VIII. Right to Debriefing

Research assistants have the right to be informed of the outcomes of the studies to which they have contributed.

Article IX. Right to Benefits for Work Performed

Research assistants have the right to fair benefits corresponding to the work they have completed. No benefits are owed for work voluntarily withdrawn from.

Article X. Right to Confidentiality in Public Acknowledgements

Research assistants have the right to choose whether their names are publicly associated with research projects in publications, presentations, or reports.

Adapted from Naufel and Beike (2013)

APPENDIX V. RESEARCHER MENTAL HEALTH SAFETY PLAN

Researcher Mental Health Safety Plan

Details

Name:

Date:

Collateral/Family Contact:

General Practitioner Contact:

Team Lead Contact:

Step 1: Triggers & Stressors

List here the behaviors, situations, and circumstances that put you at emotional risk.

- | | |
|----|----|
| 1. | 3. |
| 2. | 4. |

Step 2: Warning Signs

List here the thoughts, images, moods, situations, or behaviors that help you recognize that a crisis may be developing:

- | | |
|----|----|
| 1. | 3. |
| 2. | 4. |

Step 3: Internal Coping Strategies

Things I can do to take my mind off my problems without contacting another person (e.g., relaxation technique, physical activity)

- | | |
|----|----|
| 1. | 3. |
| 2. | 4. |

Step 4: External Coping Strategies

People and social settings that provide a distraction.

Name: Place:

Phone: Place:

Name:

Phone:

Step 5: Reliable People

Who are the people I can ask for help?

Name:	Name:
Contact:	Contact:

Name:	Name:
Contact:	Contact:

Step 6: Professionals

Who are the professionals or agencies I can contact during a crisis?

Clinician Name:

Agency:

Contact:

Contact:

Emergency #:

Emergency #:

Clinician Name:

Agency:

Contact:

Contact:

Emergency #:

Emergency #:

Suicide Prevention Lifeline Phone:

Call XXX or go to the local emergency room:

Step 7: Environment

What things can I do, or do I need to do, to make my environment safe for me?

1.

2.

The one thing that is most important to me, and worth living for, is:

Adapted from Niendam (n.d.)

APPENDIX VI. MEN4DEM RESEARCH DIARY TEMPLATE

MEN4DEM Research Diary for Risk, Harm Awareness & Self-Care

This template is designed for note-taking, with embedded questions that focus on risk and harm awareness and self-care. Each entry can be completed daily or per research-related activity. Feel free to adapt the prompts to your context and as needed.

Overview

Date:

Location:

Activity/Task Description:

Observations

- Who was present?
- What happened? (Events, actions, interactions)
- Direct quotes/transcription:
- Sketches, diagrams, photo references:

Emerging Insights & Questions

- Preliminary analytical thoughts:
- Themes or patterns noticed:
- Unanswered questions/things to follow up on:

Reflections & Emotional Check-in

- How did I feel today?
- What emotions arose during/after the task or research activity?
- Did anything feel uncomfortable or unsafe?
- Energy Levels / Stress Markers:

Risk & Safety Awareness

- Hazards/dangers observed today (environmental, logistical, interpersonal, digital):
- How were these risks managed?
- Unexpected challenges or near-misses:
- What safety steps will I take next time?

Support & Communication Log

- Did I check in with my supervisor/peers/or family?
- Did I access any support resources?
- Notes on communication or follow-ups: